

Development of a novel 4D-printed customized hand orthosis

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Abstract: 3D printing is widely used for the production of personalized, individualized orthoses. However, they cannot be adjusted after manufacturing to support the entire rehabilitation process, such as in the treatment of cerebral palsy. This treatment process is a step-by-step process that needs different adjustments for the spastic hand, whereas meeting these requirements using conventional methods or complicated mechanisms is expensive, less flexible, time-consuming, and less practical. In this research, a comprehensive investigation was conducted to additive manufacturing of the shape memory polymer hand orthosis via digital light processing (DLP). Benefiting from 4D printing's shape memory effects, adjustable through various actuating and programming parameters, fabricated orthoses could become a strong alternative treatment for cerebral palsy.

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I. Introduction

Shape memory materials are the class of smart active polymers that can memorize their permanent shape and recover it upon an external actuation. The unique properties of shape memory polymers, including lightweight, lower cost, and ease of processing and fabrication, turned them into a reliable option for medical devices. A combination of the shape memory properties and 3D printing method known as 4D printing refers to the process through which the shape of the 3D printed part changes over time upon applying external stimulus [1].

Considering the importance of using an orthotic device to treat patients suffering from cerebral palsy (hand spasticity), fabricating customized orthopaedical devices with higher performance and lower cost is a challenging endeavor. The cerebral palsy treatment in each patient could be different since they represent various body strengths and hand shapes. Moreover, since the treatment process of cerebral palsy should be accomplished gradually through stretching the spastic hand in a pain-free range, the intended orthosis must contain some positioning adjustments. Several mechanisms have been proposed to deal with this issue [2]. However, using complicated and heavy mechanisms seems expensive and uncomfortable for patients. Therefore, a demand for a more affordable as well as highly flexible approach has been raised. Addressing the issues, a customized novel hand orthosis was designed and fabricated through this research study, benefiting from 4D printing technology advantages comprising low cost, fast construction, high comfortability, and lightweight.

Indeed, utilizing 4D printing for orthosis fabrication has main advantages, making it the most suitable method for cerebral palsy treatment. Shape memory effects, known as shape recovery upon using stimulus, could be adjusted by applying different actuating and programming parameters,

such as temperature and heating time, whereby the orthosis design becomes independent of the heavy and complicated mechanisms [2].

II. Methods

Orthosis design has been classified into three main phases: anatomy acquisition, 3D orthosis modelling, and prototype construction. Figure 1 shows the procedure with the technologies used in each stage. Intermediate steps of printing and redesigning were necessary to correct and select some parameters and characteristics of the design and printing process. To capture the geometry and measurements of the affected limb, the EinScan Pro 2X 2020, a light-based scanner specifically designed for capturing body parts, has been used.

A 3D Printer was used to print the hand orthosis with a thickness of 2 mm. The parameters used for the printing process include layer thickness of 100 μm , exposure times of 2 seconds for each layer, and exposure time of 17 seconds for the three first layers to ensure that the part is attached firmly to the building plate. After the printing process, the part was thoroughly cleaned. The supports were removed using a scalper, and the surface was subsequently washed with isopropanol. The part was exposed to a UV lamp for 40 minutes to finalize the material properties to attain maximum strength.

Figure 1: Different phases of the developing process

To investigate the shape memory properties of the printed material, the shape recovery test was planned on L-shape samples with different thicknesses, including 1-, 2-, and 3-mm.

III. Results and discussion

Figure 2 indicates the shape recovery values for 90° recovery of the L-shape samples to straight form. As can be seen, the higher thickness resulted in a longer recovery time, which is on account of the longer time needed to reach isothermal temperature in the thickness direction of the sample. Besides, it was shown that higher recovery temperatures led to faster recovery of the samples, indicating that the intense reduction of the material strength in higher temperatures facilitates the shape recovery process. The images representing the full shape recovery of the L-shape samples with 2 mm thickness at 70°C were shown in the upper side of Figure 2.

Figure 2: Response time of the L-shape printed samples with different thicknesses

The customized hand orthosis was successfully 3D printed, and the programming process of the shape memory polymer was accomplished based on thermal actuation. The final product was found to be completely fitted on the scanned hand and could provide the requirements of use as an orthosis (see Figure 3).

The natural shape of the hand shall be followed by the printing process. Afterward, the programming process applies to the printed hand with a temporary shape similar to the patient's hand posture. Afterwards, the orthosis is ready to use by implementing partial recovery through the heating process as a first step of treatment and then mounting it on the patient's hand. For the next steps of the treatment process, depending on the applicable temperature for the recovery process, the orthosis could be unmounted and recovered further and then mounted again on the

patient's hand. Also, it is possible to heat the orthosis while it is mounted on the hand, provided that the low-temperature recovery is applicable.

Figure 3: Final printed hand orthosis

IV. Conclusions

The main contribution of this research study was applying the 4D-printing technique to design and fabricate the customized hand orthosis used in treating patients who have cerebral palsy. Since treating this sort of disability needs some orthopaedical devices, including step-by-step adjustment ability according to the patient's needs, the shape memory effect was utilized to provide this feature for the designated orthosis. The shape memory properties of the programmed orthosis showed that it could be actuated in a range of temperatures near the glass transition temperature or far above that by which the shape recovery and response time were adjustable.

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